

ISic2998

I.Sicily inscription 2998

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

rock

face

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2006.04; 2013.10.02

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Buscemi

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 19228

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332328

1. Λυσίμα-
2. χος, Με-
3. λίσσας πα-
4. ρὰ Παίδε-
5. σσι καὶ ἄμ [α(?)]
6. Ἄνναι ἱερεί-
7. ας, γεγέννηται
8. μετὰ [Εὐτρ(?)]ό-
9. που κα[ι] Γο-
10. νατίας καὶ
11. τῶν [ἐκ]είνου
12. συμβιωτῶν
13. καὶ Ἔρωτος
14. ναβλᾶ. vacat
15. ²pentalpha²

16.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645348

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